

Thiosalicylamide as a Reagent in Inorganic Analysis

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Thiosalicylamide has been introduced as a suitable reagent in the (a) gravimetry of the platinum metals, gold, mercury, copper, selenium and tellurium, (b) spectrophotometry of the platinum metals, gold, mercury, thallium, selenium, oxidising agents e.g., ceric sulphate, hydrogen peroxide, potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate and (c) indirect titrimetry of palladium, platinum, rhodium, copper and the oxidising agents. Thiosalicylamide is further applied as a precipitant for bismuth, cadmium, mercury and lead as sulphides from homogeneous solutions.

THE use of organic thioligands in inorganic analysis is of recent interest in analytical chemistry. The ligands containing sulphur as the coordination centre preferentially form stronger complexes with cations of larger ionic size. Under favourable conditions the vacant 3d-orbitals on sulphur being probably of low energy, are suitable for back bonding of electrons from the metals with filled or almost filled d-orbitals.

The present communication describes the various applications of thiosalicylamide(TSA), $C_6H_4(OH)CSNH_2$, as an analytical reagent. Thiosalicylamide was first prepared by Spilker¹ and was used by Krych and Lipiec² as a colorimetric reagent for iron. Shome et al³⁻¹⁷ has studied the various applicabilities of the reagent in analytical chemistry, as described below.

Thiosalicylamide as a Gravimetric Reagent

TSA forms stable insoluble complexes of definite composition with many metal ions e.g. ruthenium(II), rhodium(III), palladium(II), gold(III), mercury(II), copper(I), selenium(IV), tellurium(IV), osmium(VI or VIII), platinum(IV). The precipitates can be dried and directly weighed. The diversity in conditions under which the metal-complexes are precipitated permits the separation and simultaneous determination of the above mentioned metals. Iridium(III) is quantitatively precipitated with TSA ; but the complex gradually loses weight during drying. Hence, the metal complex may be ignited at 650°C and reduced to the metal in a current of hydrogen before weighing. The conditions under which the different metal ions are precipitated and the compositions of the complexes are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF METALS WITH THIOSALICYLAMIDE

Metal ion	Acidity for quantitative precipitation	Composition of the complex (dried at °C)
Copper(I) ³	0.1-1.0M HCl	$Cu_2(C_7H_7ONS)_4Cl_2$ (110-120)
Gold (III) ⁴	3.0-6.0M HCl	$Au(C_7H_7ONS)_3Cl$, $6H_2O$ (105) $Au(C_7H_7ONS)_3Cl$ (135)
Mercury(II) ⁵	0.1-2.0M HCl	$Hg(C_7H_7ONS)_2Cl_2$ (110-120)
Selenium(IV) ⁶	pH 1.0-2.2	$Se(C_7H_7ONS)_3 OH$ (110-120)
Tellurium(IV) ⁷	pH 1.0-2.16	$Te(C_7H_7ONS)_2 (OH)_2$ (110-120)
Ruthenium(II) ⁸	pH 3.8-6.0	$Ru(C_7H_6ONS)_2$ (110-120)
Rhodium(III) ⁸	pH 4.5-6.5	$Rh(C_7H_6ONS)_3$ (110-120)
Palladium(II) ⁸	2.0-8.0M HCl	$Pd(C_7H_7ONS)_4Cl_2$ (110-120)
Osmium(VI/VIII) ⁴	pH 2.5-7.0	$OsO_2(C_7H_6ONS)_2$ (110-120)
Iridium(III) ⁹	pH 4.6-5.8	—
Platinum(IV) ¹⁰	1.0-6.0N HCl pH 5.0-6.0	$Pt(C_7H_6ONS)_2 (C_7H_7ONS)_2Cl_2$ (105) $Pt(C_7H_6ONS)_2$ (140)

Gravimetric separation of the metal ions is indicated in Table III.

Thiosalicylamide as a Spectrophotometric reagent for Metal Ions

The complexes formed by TSA with metal ions e.g. ruthenium(II), rhodium(III), palladium(II), osmium(VI or VIII), iridium(III), platinum(IV), gold(III), mercury(II), thallium(III), selenium(IV) are coloured and soluble in organic solvents. TSA has, therefore, been employed as a spectrophotometric reagent for the above metal ions. Suitable adjustment of the experimental conditions and the use of masking agents, e.g. fluoride, phosphate, tartrate and EDTA increase the selectivity of the reagent. Table II furnishes the data for the evaluation of TSA as a spectrophotometric reagent for the various metal ions. Spectrophotometric separation of the metal ions is reported in Table III.

Thiosalicylamide as a Spectrophotometric reagent for Oxidising Agents¹⁴ :

TSA is quantitatively oxidised in acidic medium

by strong oxidising agents like hydrogen peroxide, ceric sulphate, potassium dichromate, potassium permanganate to an intense red oxidation product of mole-

cular formula $\text{HO.C}_6\text{H}_5-\overset{\text{NH}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{S}-\text{S}-\overset{\text{NH}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OH}$. The oxidation potential of the redox system $2\text{RH} \rightleftharpoons \text{R}-\text{R}+2\text{H}^++2\text{e}$ [where $\text{RH}=\text{HO.C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{C}(\text{SH})=\text{NH}$] is 0.5140V. The intense red oxidation product is readily soluble in ethanol, chloroform, benzene and other common organic solvents. The measurement of colour intensity of the red chloroform extract provides an indirect method for the determination of those oxidants in trace amounts colorimetrically. The chloroform solution of the oxidation product shows maximum absorbance at 460 nm. The optimum acidity for the quantitative oxidation of TSA by hydrogen peroxide, potassium dichromate, ceric sulphate and potassium permanganate are 3.5-5.0N, 2.0-3.5N, 2.5-4.0N and 3.5-5.5N sulphuric acid respectively. The sensitivity of the colour systems are $0.0350 \mu\text{g Ce}^{4+} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $0.0086 \mu\text{g Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $0.0263 \mu\text{g MnO}_4^- \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $0.0053 \mu\text{g H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

TABLE II—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF METALS WITH THIOSALICYLAMIDE.

Metal Ion	Solvent	Acidity for complete extraction	Concentration range	λ_{max} (nm)	Metal to reagent ratio in the complex	Molar extinction coefficient	Sensitivity $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$
Gold(III) ⁴	Chloroform	2.0-4.0M HCl	2.78-16.68 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	460	1:4	10.06×10^3	0.0196
Mercury(II) ⁵	50% Ethanol	pH2.0-2.95	3.90-23.40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	355	1:4	5.878×10^3	0.034
Thallium(III) ¹¹	Chloroform	2-3.5NH ₂ SO ₄	2.80-56.00 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	458	1:2	5100 ± 10	0.04
Selenium(IV) ¹²	Chloroform	pH1.4-2.6	0.33-5.28 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	460	—	11.62×10^3	0.0068
Ruthenium (II) ⁸	Methylisobutyl ketone	pH3.1-4.2	1.10-5.20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	385	—	63.30×10^3	0.01603
Rhodium(III) ⁸	„	pH4.2-6.5	1.25-4.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	377	1:3	70.14×10^3	0.0148
Palladium(II) ⁸	50% Ethanol	pH1.2 to 3.5M HCl	0.5-1.06 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	350	1:4	39.28×10^3	0.0027
Osmium(VI/VIII) ⁴	Methylisobutyl ketone	pH4.5-6.0	3.0-15.4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	385	—	66.14×10^3	0.0287
Iridium(III) ¹³	„	pH5.4-6.3	1.84-9.20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	400	1:3	1.06×10^4	0.018
Platinum(IV) ¹⁰	Chloroform	3.0-45NHCl	2.80-9.18 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	430	1:4	1.23×10^4	0.016

TABLE III—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF METALS.

Metals	Foreign Ions causing no Interference in Gravimetry	Foreign Ions causing no Interference in Spectrophotometry.
Cu(I)	Fe, Ni, Co, Mn, Zn, Cd, Pb, Bi, V, Ti, Sn ;	—
Au(III)	Co, Ni, Mn, U, Mo, Ir(IV), Rh, Ru ;	Co, Ni, Mn, Fe ^a , V ^a , Rh, Ir(IV), U ;
Hg(II)	Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, Cd, Al, Cr, Fe ^a , Ti, Mo, U, As, Sb, Pb, Bi ;	Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, Cd, Cr, Al, Fe ^a , Ti, Mo, U, As, Sb, Pb, Bi ;
Tl(III)	—	Ni, Co, Mn, Zn, Cd, Cr, Ga, In, Al, Ti, U, V ;
Se(IV)	Co, Ni, Mn, Cd, Th, Al ^b , Ga ^b , In ^b , W ^b , Cu ^c , Zn ^c , Fe ^c , Te* ; Mo ^b ;	Mn, Co, Ni, Cd, Al, Th, U, Cu ^c , Fe ^b , W ^b , Mo ^b ;
Te(IV)	Co, Ni, Mn, Cr, Cd, Zn, U, Al ^b , Ga ^b , In ^b , Th ^b , Mo ^b , W ^b , Cu ^c , Fe ^c , Se* ;	—
Ru(II)	Pd*, Pt*, Os*, Ir(IV), Au*, Hg*, Co ^b , Ni ^b , Cu ^c , V ^b , Zn ^b ;	Pd*, Au*, Pt*, Os*, Ir(IV), Co ^b , Ni ^b , Mn ^b , Zn ^b , Fe ^b , Cr ^b , Cu ^c , U ^b ;
Rh(III)	Pd*, Pt*, Os*, Hg*, Au*, Cu ^c , Fe ^b , Co ^b , Ni ^b , Mn ^b , Zn ^b , V ^b , W ^b ;	Pt*, Os*, Pd*, Au*, Ir(IV), Mn ^b , Co ^b , Ni ^b , Cd ^b , Zn ^b , Fe ^b , Cu ^c ;
Pd(II)	Rh, Ru, Os*, Ir(IV), Co, Ni, Mn, Zn, Fe ^a , Cr, U ;	Ru, Rh, Ir, Os*, Mn, Ni, Co, Zn, Fe ^a , Cr ;
Ir(III)	Pd*, Pt*, Au*, Os*, Co ^b , Ni ^b , Zn ^b , Mn ^b , Mo ^b , Cu ^c , Ti ^b , U ^b , Pb ^c ;	Pd*, Pt*, Au*, Ru*, Os*, Co ^b , Ni ^b , Mn ^b , Zn ^b , Cd ^b , Fe ^b , Cu ^c , Pb ^c , ;
Os(VI/VIII)	Ir(IV), Fe ^a , Co ^b , Ni ^b , Zn ^b , Mn ^b , Mo ^b , Ti ^b , U ^b , V ^b , Cu ^c ;	Ir(IV), Fe ^b , Co ^b , Ni ^b , Cr ^b , Ti ^b , V ^b , Mo ^b , Cu ^c , Pd, Au ;
Pt(IV)	Ir(IV), Ru, Rh, Os*, Co, Ni, Mn, Zn, Cd, Fe ^a , U, Mo ;	Ir(IV), Rh, Ru, Co, Ni, Mn, Zn, Cd, Cr, U, Mo ;
Pt(II)	Ir(IV), Co ^b , Ni ^b , Mn ^b , Zn ^b , Fe ^b , V ^b , U ^b , Cu ^c ;	—

a=In presence of phosphate ; b=In presence of tartrate ; c=In presence of EDTA ; *=Prior separation

Thiosalicylamide as a Primary Standard in Iodometry

Pure TSA can be used as a primary standard in the iodometric determination of some oxidising anions and cations. In acid medium TSA is oxidised by iodine solution producing a red water insoluble product which makes it difficult to locate the exact end point in iodometric titration. However, at pH 6.0-7.5, TSA is quantitatively oxidised with iodine producing a colourless water soluble product. The oxidation product has been isolated, recrystallised and found to be *o*-hydroxybenzoxonitrile,

The formal oxidation potential of the above redox reaction has been measured potentiometrically and found to be 0.40 volts (at pH 6.5). The equivalent

weight of TSA (mol. wt. 153) is 19.125 (1/8th of the molecular weight) as one mole of the reagent reacts with four moles of iodine. Iodine solution is standardised with an aqueous solution (0.1N) of TSA using the latter as a primary standard at pH 6.0-7.5 using starch as an indicator. Potassium dichromate, potassium permanganate, ceric sulphate, potassium bromate and hydrogen peroxide are then determined with TSA by the usual iodometric procedure at pH 6.5-7.5. The copper content in brass and bronze is also determined iodometrically by the use of TSA. The results obtained by the above method when compared with those obtained by the standard procedures using sodium thiosulphate solution as the secondary standard are found to be in good agreement. However, in the estimation of Ce(IV) ions TSA is found to be more suitable since high results are generally obtained when cerium is determined iodometrically using thiosulphate as the titrant.

Volumetric Determination of Palladium, Platinum and Rhodium¹⁶.

TSA reacts quantitatively with palladium(II), platinum(IV) and rhodium(III) forming stable complexes of known composition under specified conditions as given in Table I. The use of TSA has been investigated for the titrimetric determination of palladium(II), platinum(IV) and rhodium(III) by precipitation of the metal complexes with a measured excess of standard thiosalicylamide solution and subsequent back titration of the excess reagent (after filtration of the precipitate) with standard iodine solution at pH 6.5-7.5 [1 ml 1*N* thiosalicylamide (consumed for complex formation) \equiv 1 ml 1*N* iodine solution \equiv 3.334 mg of Pd/6.096 mg of Pt/4.288 mg Rh. Palladium or Platinum can be determined in the presence of rhodium(III), ruthenium(III) or iridium(III). Simultaneous determinations of the metals in the mixtures of rhodium-palladium and rhodium-platinum are also possible by the above method. From a mixture of Pd⁺²-Rh⁺³ and Pt⁺⁴-Rh⁺³, Pd⁺² or Pt⁺⁴ is first directly estimated by precipitating the metal in 2-3*N* HCl medium with a measured excess of TSA. The excess reagent is then titrated with standard iodine solution at pH 6.5-7.5 and from the amount of the reagent consumed for complexation, the quantity of the corresponding metal ion is calculated. For the determination of rhodium in the above mixtures, palladium or platinum is precipitated with the same amount of reagent used as before in 2-3*N* HCl medium, and filtered. The filtrate and the washing is then adjusted to pH 4.5-6.5 and heated on a boiling water bath for complete precipitation of rhodium. It is cooled to room temperature, and filtered. The filtrate is adjusted to pH 6.5-7.5 and titrated with standard iodine solution. The volume of the iodine solution needed for titration of excess of the reagent after precipitation of palladium (or platinum) minus the volume of the iodine solution required for excess of TSA after complexation with palladium (or platinum) and rhodium gives the iodine equivalent of rhodium only.

Thiosalicylamide as a Precipitating agent from Homogeneous solution¹⁷

TSA forms metal sulphides with certain metal ions and is used for the quantitative precipitation of

mercury (II), cadmium (II), bismuth (III) and lead (II) as sulphides from homogeneous solutions in almost neutral medium. The pH range for the precipitation of the metal sulphides is from 6.5 to 7.0. The sulphides are washed once with hot water, twice with cold water, finally with a mixture of ethanol and ether, and weighed after drying at 100°-105°C. The sulphur contamination in the precipitated sulphides is negligibly small, which is a distinct advantage over the other precipitants for metal sulphides e.g., thioacetic acid, thioacetamide etc. Further, mercury can be separated from cadmium, lead and bismuth with TSA using a mixture of EDTA²⁻ and tartrate ions as masking agents. Cadmium can be determined in presence of mercury using cyanides as masking agent. In the presence of excess EDTA²⁻ ions, cadmium, lead and bismuth ions do not form any precipitate with TSA. In presence of tartrate ions, cadmium and lead are precipitated with the reagent. The precipitation of bismuth ions with the reagent is quantitative in presence of a mixture of tartrate and acetate ions. However, low results are obtained when tartrate ions are present in large excess.

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